

A Survey on Enhancing Training Efficiency of Large Transformer Models for Text Classification in NLP

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Abstract

In recent years, the advent of large transformer models has revolutionized the field of natural language processing, leading to remarkable advances in text classification tasks. However, there is a huge dependency on computational resources, which increases as the size of the model increases, leading to an increase in the training time and costs. In this survey, we analyze and compare methods that save computation and memory costs during training, together with techniques on hardware/algorithm co-design. We finally discuss challenges and promising areas for future research. We also investigate a spectrum of strategies aimed at enhancing the efficiency of text classification using large transformer models, while concurrently preserving state-of-the-art accuracy and reducing computational time. By meticulously exploring techniques such as model pruning, knowledge distillation, and specialized hardware utilization, this study presents a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art approaches. Moreover, it delves into the intersection of efficiency gains and environmental sustainability, illustrating how optimized model architectures can significantly contribute to a greener computational ecosystem. This survey not only provides a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners in the field but also underscores the critical importance of balancing performance gains with environmental responsibility in developing and deploying advanced NLP models.

Index Terms

Transformer Models, Model Pruning, Knowledge Distillation, Environmental Sustainability, Computational Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of deep learning depends on the vast computational resources available and extremely large amounts of labeled data. In light of the substantial advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP), the proliferation of deep learning models, particularly Transformers, has introduced significant challenges due to their size and computational demands. At a foundational level, two pressing issues have emerged [1]. The primary challenge pertains to the computational intensity associated with training large Transformer-based models, as expounded by [2]. A widely discussed research on the energy consumption of deep learning models suggests that employing neural architecture search (NAS) to train a Transformer base model results in approximately 626,155 pounds of carbon dioxide emissions, which is equivalent to the cumulative emissions of five cars over their lifetimes [3]. As these models increase in size, their computational requirements surpass advancements in hardware efficiency. It becomes extremely important to make deep learning tenable in terms of computation and energy efficiency.

The second obstacle arises from the escalating training memory, directly proportional to the size of attention-based models, as highlighted in the literature [1]. BERT models are costly to train and develop, financially, due to the cost of hardware and electricity or cloud computing time, and environmentally, due to the carbon footprint required to fuel modern tensor processing hardware.

As a result, training a state-of-the-art model now requires substantial computational resources which demand considerable energy, along with the associated financial and environmental costs. Many NLP models now require multiple instances of specialized hardware such as GPUs or TPUs, which are expensive, thereby limiting access to these highly accurate models. Even when these expensive computational resources are available to the public, model training incurs a substantial cost to the environment due to the energy required to power this hardware for weeks or months.

Scaling has become a key ingredient in achieving state-of-the-art performance in NLP, as recent research suggests that some capabilities only emerge once models grow beyond a certain size. However, despite the merits of scaling, it poses key challenges to making these breakthroughs accessible in resource-constrained environments, in having a non-negligible environmental impact, and in complying with hardware constraints. To tackle these limitations, there has been a renewed focus on research that seeks to improve model efficiency.

In this work, we focus on enhancing these 3 perspectives of large transformer models: noitemsep

- Reduction in training time

- Environmental Impact
- Cost of running models

A. *Reduction in Training time*

Training time is a critical aspect in the development of transformer models, particularly in the context of natural language processing (NLP) tasks. The efficiency and speed at which a model can be trained directly impact its feasibility for practical applications. By exploring various approaches, including knowledge distillation and structured pruning, we aim to uncover insights that can significantly reduce the time and resources required for training while maintaining acceptable levels of accuracy.

In this survey, we study the different techniques employed by researchers to reduce the training time of large transformer models. We investigate the implications of knowledge distillation, structured pruning, and model quantization in pursuing faster and more cost-effective training processes. We provide insights into optimizing the training time of transformer models.

B. *Environmental impact*

The environmental impact of AI, especially in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), has become a significant concern due to the growing energy consumption associated with training and operating computational models. According to [4], there is currently a lack of clear guidelines for systematically reporting the environmental impact of NLP research. In response, [4] proposed a climate performance model card with the primary purpose of being practically usable with only limited information about experiments and the underlying computer hardware.

C. *Cost of running models*

Training and developing large Transformer Models incur significant financial expenses attributed to hardware, electricity, and cloud compute time. Illustratively, GPT-3 [5], the precursor to ChatGPT, underwent training on half a trillion words with approximately 175 billion parameters. To provide insight into the scale, the technical overview of GPT-32 reveals that a single training run would demand 355 GPU-years and cost a minimum of \$4.6M. This estimation considers a theoretical 28 TFLOPS for V100 and the lowest 3-year reserved cloud pricing. Consequently, the groundbreaking achievements in deep learning, exemplified by models like ChatGPT, are predominantly driven by large and affluent enterprises such as Google or Microsoft.

II. RELATED WORK

This section describes the work done in three crucial aspects that shape the landscape of transformer models in natural language processing:

- Reduction in Training Time
- Environmental Impact
- Cost of Running Models

A. *Reduction in training time*

Fastformers [6] significantly improve how efficiently large language models run by using three key techniques: Knowledge Distillation, Structured Pruning, and Model Quantization. These methods are like tools that help the model process information much faster. Testing this approach on the SuperGLUE benchmark, Fastformers achieved impressive speed-ups compared to standard models: up to 233.9x faster on CPU and 12.4x faster on GPU. For example, by removing certain parts of the model (pruning), Fastformers achieved a 2.97x speed-up on CPU but lost 1.9 points of accuracy. This shows that finding the right balance between speed and accuracy is important. The impact of pruning can vary depending on the task. In the Record task, pruning resulted in a 1.95x speed-up but with a higher accuracy loss of 12.1 points. This highlights the need to consider the specific task at hand when applying these optimization techniques. Structured pruning is applied to achieve a balance between model size reduction and task accuracy. The pruned model is then fine-tuned through knowledge distillation using an iterative approach, resulting in improved accuracy for the pruned model. After knowledge distillation and structured pruning compression, utilizing 8-bit or 16-bit lower precision arithmetic has been demonstrated to maintain acceptable accuracy for Transformer models.

[7] propose a method to train a smaller, student model to mimic the predictions of a larger, teacher model. This is achieved by using a soft target distribution, which is the probability distribution over the outputs of the teacher model [7]. The student model is then trained to minimize the Kullback-Leibler divergence between its predictions and the soft target distribution. The authors found that by using knowledge distillation, they were able to train student models that were significantly smaller than the teacher model, with only a small loss in accuracy.

[8] proposes a new approach to training transformer models that are both smaller and faster than existing models. The approach uses two techniques: quantization-aware training and tensor compression [8]. Quantization-aware training allows the

model to be trained with lower precision weights, which reduces the model size. Tensor compression reduces the number of parameters in the model by compressing the embedding and linear layers into small low-rank tensor cores. The authors show that their approach can achieve up to 63x compression with little accuracy loss and remarkable inference and training speedup.

[9] discusses the training of state-of-the-art NLP models for two tasks: self-supervised pretraining using masked language modeling and high-resource machine translation and the relationship between increased resources, such as larger model sizes and more extensive datasets, along with their impact on model accuracy. It suggests that self-supervised pretraining has improved model performance. To address computational constraints, the text recommends rethinking the assumption that models must converge during training and proposes terminating training earlier for larger models. Experimental results with Transformer models show that larger models achieve lower validation errors with fewer gradient updates, despite increased computational demands. However, larger models raise concerns about computational and memory requirements during inference, which are addressed through efficient compression techniques, with ROBERTA being particularly compressible [10]. In summary, the text emphasizes the advantages of larger models in data-rich scenarios where overfitting is less of a concern and attributes their enhanced compressibility to overparameterization.

B. Environmental Impact

A lot of researchers have worked in terms of the energy consumption and environmental impact of large transformer models. [11] performed a comparative analysis of the energy required to train a variety of popular off-the-shelf NLP models, as well as a case study of the complete sum of resources required to develop LISA, a state-of-the-art NLP model from EMNLP 2018, including all tuning and experimentation. They concluded on 3 points: noitemsep

- 1) Authors should report training time and sensitivity to hyperparameters.
- 2) Academic researchers need equitable access to computation resources.
- 3) Researchers should prioritize computationally efficient hardware and algorithms.

TABLE I
A SURVEY OF RESEARCH PAPERS FOCUSED ON ENHANCING THE TRAINING TIMES OF LARGE TRANSFORMER MODELS

Sr. no	Ref.	Findings	Limitations
1	[6]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On GPU, up to 12.4x speed-up with the presented methods was achieved. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A loss of 1.9 points in accuracy by pruning.
2	[8]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 63x compression with little accuracy loss and remarkable inference and training speedup. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The approach is not able to compress all layers of a transformer model equally effectively. Accuracy loss.
3	[9]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Best strategy for resource-constrained training is to train large models and then heavily compress them. Large models train faster than small models, even though they require more computing resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The paper only evaluates the proposed approach on two transformer models, BERT and Roberta. It is possible that the results may not generalize to other transformer models or to other NLP tasks. Does not compare the proposed approach to other state-of-the-art model compression techniques, such as knowledge distillation and low-rank approximation.
4	[12]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved the performance of an ensemble of 10 models by 1% by using knowledge distillation. The authors evaluate their method on the MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets and show that it can achieve comparable or even better results than traditional training methods. Smaller, student model mimics the predictions of a larger, teacher model. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0.5% loss in accuracy on the MNIST dataset. Knowledge distillation can be sensitive to the choice of temperature.
5	[13]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bottleneck/inverted bottleneck structures enable effective layer-wise knowledge transfer. MobileBERT is 4.3x smaller and 5.5x faster than BERTBASE while achieving competitive results on GLUE. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Achieves a GLUE score of 77.7 (0.6 lower than BERTBASE).

'Green AI', an emerging focus at the Allen Institute for AI, refers to AI research that yields novel results without increasing computational cost, and ideally reducing it [5]. Some important green directions suggested by 'Green AI' include: Research on building space or time-efficient models is often motivated by fitting a model on a small device (such as a phone) or fast enough to process examples in real-time, such as image captioning for the blind. For some modern models that don't even fit on a single GPU, they argue for a far broader approach.

The total number of experiments run to get a final result is often under-reported and under-discussed [14]. A finding reported by [15] showed that stopping training early for models that are clearly underperforming can lead to great savings. While many hyperparameter optimization algorithms exist that can reduce the computational expense required to reach a given level of performance [16] [17], simple improvements here can have a large impact.

[18] provides a comprehensive examination of the environmental impact associated with the creation of a set of four expansive language models known as the Noor models. This assessment takes into consideration diverse factors, encompassing

Fig. 1. A study conducted by 'Green AI' shows AI papers tend to target accuracy rather than efficiency [5]

data collection and storage, research and development, pretraining, personnel costs (including international flights for training workshops), as well as future serving and inference. The total estimated carbon emissions for the project amount to 36.5 tons of CO₂. Notably, the majority (65%) of these emissions stem from the training phase of the models, while 18% are attributed to international flights, 12% to data storage, and 4% to small-scale research and development experiments.

They highlight that the primary driver of the carbon footprint is the carbon intensity of the energy sources used for model training. It suggests that choosing the location for computations can significantly reduce the environmental impact, with the example of conducting all computations in France reducing the total footprint to 14.9 tons of CO₂, with a significant portion (42%) still attributed to international flights.

Practitioners are encouraged to inform users about efficient inference practices and environmentally friendly computation practices, such as selecting efficient data centers and running inference in regions with a low environmental impact energy mix. They state that efficient architectures, inference, implementations, hardware, and data center choice can play a vital role in reducing the carbon footprint of future projects.

C. Cost of running models

[5] proposes reporting the financial cost or “price tag” of developing, training, and running models to provide baselines for the investigation of increasingly efficient methods. papers could be required to plot accuracy as a function of computational cost and training set size, providing a baseline for more data-efficient research in the future [5]. According to them, when considering the different factors that increase the computational and environmental cost of producing such a result, three factors should be considered: the cost of executing the model on a single (E)xample (either during training or at inference time); the size of the training (D)ataset, which controls the number of times the model is executed during training, and the number of (H)yperparameter experiments, which controls how many times the model is trained during model development. The total cost of producing a (R)esult in machine learning increases linearly with each of these quantities. This cost can be estimated as follows:

$$Cost(R) \propto E * D * H$$

Equation 1: The equation of Red AI: where the cost of an AI (R)esult grows linearly with the cost of processing a single (E)xample, the size of the training (D)ataset and the number of (H)yperparameter experiments [5].

III. LANDSCAPE OF EFFICIENCY-ENHANCING TECHNIQUES

This section explores various techniques for enhancing the efficiency of large language models, focusing on approaches that reduce the model size or computational cost without sacrificing performance.

A. Learning techniques

Learning techniques train a model differently with a smaller model, to improve the quality of a baseline model, where the smaller model has a lesser number of parameters/layers in the model than the base model [20]. A benefit of learning techniques is that they are applied only to the training without impacting the inference.

1) **Knowledge distillation:** Knowledge distillation is a compression technique, where a larger model (teacher) is used to train a smaller model (student). The student model tries to mimic the behavior of the teacher model. trained a single large neural net with two hidden layers on the MNIST dataset. They also performed experiments on speech recognition. They explain that neural networks produce class probabilities by using a “softmax” output layer that converts the logit computed for each class into a probability. They use the teacher model to generate soft labels on existing labeled data. The soft labels assign a probability to each class. In the paper, [7] were able to closely match the accuracy of a 10-model ensemble for a speech recognition task with a single distilled model.

TABLE II
A SURVEY OF RESEARCH PAPERS FOCUSED ON REDUCING THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND FINANCIAL COSTS OF LARGE TRANSFORMER MODEL

Sr. no	Ref.	Findings	Limitations
1	[4]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The authors propose a climate performance model card that would be included with every NLP model release. Climate performance model cards would improve the reporting of environmental impact, making it easier to track and compare the impact of different models. Facilitate the development of more efficient NLP models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate awareness alone does not guarantee behavior change. Behavior change, such as researchers and practitioners taking steps to mitigate their adverse effects and make positive contributions, is not solely determined by awareness and values.
2	[5]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The authors propose reporting the financial cost or “price tag” of developing, training, and running models to provide baselines for the investigation of increasingly efficient methods. One simple technique to improve in this area is to report performance with different amounts of training data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Red AI, which refers to AI research that seeks to obtain state-of-the-art results in accuracy (or related measures) through the use of massive computational power, is more prevalent.
3	[11]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers should prioritize computationally efficient hardware and algorithms. They also estimate that the CO2 emissions associated with training an LLM can range from hundreds of kilograms to tons. The authors find that the cost of training an LLM can range from thousands of dollars to millions of dollars, depending on the size and complexity of the model. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Noted that the advances have come at a cost, as training LLMs can require a significant amount of energy and computing resources.
4	[18]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The total estimated carbon emissions for the project are 36.5 tons of CO2, with the majority (65%) attributed to training the models, 18% from international flights, 12% from data storage, and 4% from small-scale research and development experiments. Despite being trained using a number of efficiency measures, Noor still has a significant carbon footprint, equivalent to the emissions of 165 cars driven over the course of a year. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Despite being trained using a number of efficiency measures, Noor still has a significant carbon footprint, equivalent to the emissions of 165 cars driven over the course of a year.
5	[19]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The authors propose a new method for energy measurement that uses a hardware power meter. The method evaluated on 4 different NLP models for a question-answering task performs significantly more accurately than existing software-based methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex energy issues within the model, such as tail power and energy distribution across hardware components, remain unexplored and deferred to future investigations. If one needs to understand the energy spent inside the model for a single inference, the energy values are still coarse-grained.

[6] employed two distinct distillation strategies, specifically task-specific and task-agnostic distillation. In task-specific distillation, they distilled fine-tuned teacher models into smaller student architectures, following the approach outlined by TinyBERT [21]. For task-agnostic distillation, they directly applied fine-tuning on general distilled models to adapt to a specific task. Notably, in the task-specific scenario, the researchers observed that the initialization of student models played a crucial role in determining the final accuracy of the distilled models. Open-domain pre-distilled models, such as distilrobertabase, were utilized as initializers for the corresponding student models. Their experiments revealed that distilled models exhibited suboptimal performance when distilled into a different model type. The Fastformers model showcased impressive speed-ups ranging from 9.8x to 233.9x compared to out-of-the-box models on CPU, and on GPU, the presented methods achieved speed-ups of up to 12.4x. ¹ and TinyBERT ²

Fig. 2. Knowledge distillation of a smaller student model from a larger teacher model.

DistilBERT [12] shares a similar overall architecture with BERT, with the removal of token-type embeddings and the pooler, and a halving of the number of layers. The study conducted by [12] revealed that changes in the number of layers exert a more significant influence on computational efficiency than other factors. DistilBERT is specifically designed to address this

¹<https://huggingface.co/distilroberta-base>

²<https://github.com/huawei-noah/Pretrained-Language-Model/tree/master/TinyBERT>

by focusing on reducing the number of layers. Impressively, they were able to maintain 97% of BERT's performance while boasting 40% fewer parameters and achieving a 60% increase in speed compared to BERT.

B. Model compression techniques

This section deals with model compression techniques such as Pruning and Quantization. Types of pruning include structured pruning, unstructured pruning, movement pruning, magnitude pruning and more. Quantization involves converting a floating point bits to smaller bits such as integer bits.

1) **Pruning**: Pruning is a data compression technique that reduces the number of parameters such as weight connections and bias in a model to decrease training time and model size. Structured Pruning streamlines neural networks by trimming self-attention heads and hidden states in feedforward layers, boosting efficiency while maintaining accuracy. [6] observed that the pruned model can get better accuracy when it goes through another round of knowledge distillation. This has also been noted in [22]. Therefore, they do one more round of knowledge distillation by using the non-pruned model as a teacher model and the pruned model as an initializer of the student model.

Combining pruning with quantization has been a notable approach in model optimization. [23] successfully pruned state-of-the-art CNN models without sacrificing accuracy. Building on this, [24] extended the approach by utilizing pruning to reduce the number of connections by 9x to 13x and quantization to decrease the number of bits representing each connection from 32 to 5. The integration of network quantization and weight sharing further compressed the pruned network by reducing the bits required to represent each weight. Interestingly, their observations revealed that when applied independently, the accuracy of a pruned network starts to significantly decline when compressed below 8% of its original size, and similarly, the accuracy of a quantized network drops significantly below 8% compression. However, when combined, the network can be compressed to 3% of its original size with no loss of accuracy.

Fig. 3. Pruning weights (connections) and neurons in a neural network.

2) **Quantization**: The quantization-based approach aims to achieve substantial model compression at the cost of affordable loss of model accuracy. By converting high-precision floating-point values into lower-precision integers or discrete representations, quantization significantly enhances model efficiency. This translates to faster computations and reduced memory footprint, making it ideal for deploying models on resource-constrained devices like mobile phones [13].

Based on the components they target, quantization methods fall into three categories: (1) weight quantization, (2) activation quantization and (3) fixed-point quantization [8]. Weight quantization represents model weights using fewer bits. Activation quantization quantizes the intermediate values i.e. activations that arise during model inference. Fixed-point quantization represents weights and activations using fixed-point arithmetic to reduce memory usage and accelerate computations.

Fig. 4. Model quantization involving a reduction in the number of bits from 32-bit to 8-bit.

IV. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND EMERGING TRENDS

At the forefront of NLP research, optimizing large transformer models remains a critical challenge. This section explores promising research avenues and anticipates future advancements that will shape efficiency gains.

A. Promising Areas for Further Research

The landscape of efficiency enhancement in large transformer models is poised for continued evolution. Promising areas for future research include the exploration of novel pruning techniques that target specific layers or attention heads to achieve finer-grained model reductions. Additionally, investigating dynamic quantization methods and experimenting with hybrid precision schemes holds the potential for further improving the balance between accuracy and efficiency.

Furthermore, the integration of reinforcement learning and meta-learning approaches for knowledge distillation presents an exciting avenue for advancing the state-of-the-art in model compression. Research in this area aims to refine existing techniques and uncover new avenues for achieving greater efficiency gains.

B. Anticipated Technological Developments

Anticipated technological advancements are expected to play a pivotal role in shaping the landscape of efficiency enhancement for large transformer models. The advent of more powerful and energy-efficient hardware, such as next-generation GPUs and TPUs, is likely to open new possibilities for accelerating model training and inference. Additionally, advancements in algorithmic optimizations tailored specifically for transformer architectures are expected to further enhance efficiency gains.

Furthermore, developments in model architecture design, such as the exploration of sparse attention mechanisms and structured matrices, are anticipated to yield breakthroughs in both computational efficiency and model performance. As these technologies continue to mature, they are likely to catalyze innovative approaches to tackling the efficiency challenges in NLP.

V. CONCLUSION

This survey paper has provided a comprehensive overview of efficiency enhancement strategies for text classification using large transformer models. Through an in-depth exploration of seminal research papers, we have examined techniques such as model pruning, quantization, knowledge distillation, specialized hardware utilization, architectural modifications, and hybrid approaches. These strategies have demonstrated remarkable potential in reducing computational demands without compromising accuracy. Efficiency enhancement in large transformer models holds significant implications for the broader field of NLP and environmental sustainability. By streamlining the computational requirements of these models, researchers and practitioners can make NLP applications more accessible and environmentally responsible. The integration of specialized hardware, knowledge distillation, and architectural modifications not only advances the state-of-the-art in NLP but also contributes to a greener computational ecosystem. In an era marked by heightened environmental consciousness, the responsible development and deployment of large transformer models underscore our commitment to a sustainable future. This survey advocates for a balanced approach, emphasizing the imperative of efficiency gains that align with environmental responsibility, setting the stage for a more sustainable and impactful future in NLP research and applications.

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